

APPLICATION OF BIOTECHNOLOGICAL TOOLS FOR COMMON BEAN (*Phaseolus vulgaris L.*) IMPROVEMENT

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Abstract

Common bean is the most common food legume crop in the world. Beans comprise an important source of dietary protein for over half a billion people mainly in developing countries. Across farming systems, biotic and abiotic stresses continue to present the major constraints for increased bean production and high yields with bean diseases representing the major constraints to production by reducing yields and seed quality. The progress in genetic and breeding improvement of bean, applying classical methods reached to his limits in many attitudes. Due to a long process of breeding and selection, the bean genetic diversity has been very limited. Bean breeding programmes are well developed, but there are many limitations of the traditionally breeding methods coming from the low recombination potential due to the selfing process, low heritability of some important characteristics (total yields and yield components), and embryo abortion of some inter specific hybrids, etc. Then, alongside the conventional breeding techniques, a biotechnological tool such as tissues culture, in vitro mutagenesis, Identification of quantitative trait loci (QTLs) with marker assisted breeding and genetic transformation has been made to obtain improved common bean varieties. Transgenic and Omics based technologies have been shown to be powerful tools holding a tremendous promise for the future.

Keywords: Transgenic, Omics, QTL, Marker-Assisted Selection, Tissues culture

Introduction

Common bean varieties can be classified into two major gene pools within the species based on their overall seed size and origin in terms of domestication and center of diversity (Singh *et al.* 1991a). Studies by means of molecular analyses in common bean strongly support the existence of two primary centers of origin known as the Mesoamerican (small to medium-sized) and Andean (large seed type) regions (Blair *et al.*, 2006). *Phaseolus* genus contains approximately 70 species and within this genus, common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris L.*) is a diploid ($2n = 2x = 22$) and predominantly self crossing species although 3% or more out crossing ratio has also been observed (Ibarra-Perez *et al.*, 1997). It is now widespread and cultivated as a major food crop in many tropical, subtropical and temperate areas of the Americas, Europe, Africa and Asia (Wortmann, 2006).

Worldwide statistics on common bean are difficult to collect, as the various *Phaseolus* and *vigna* species are often lumped together. According to FAO, dry beans production (theoretically only *Phaseolus* species) was about 23 million t in 2012, cultivated on 29 million ha. Myanmar, India, Brazil, China, USA, Mexico and Tanzania represented 2/3 of the world production of dry beans while China was the main producer of fresh beans (*Phaseolus* and *Vigna* species: 17 million t in 2011, 77% of the world production) (FAO, 2013). According to other sources, 30% of common bean production comes from South America. Common bean is less known in Asia where other grain legumes are preferred (Ecoport, 2013). However, production in China is

important: estimated acreage in the 2010s was about 0.6 million ha (Cheng Xuzhen *et al.*, 2011). Across all of Africa, a total of 4 million hectares are planted annually with a total production of around 2.8 million tons (Broughton *et al.* 2003). During the 2014/15 cropping year, Ethiopia produced 5137248.07 Quintals of common bean (White and Red) on 323327.27 ha of land and the farmers was achieved 18.45Quintal/Hectare Yield, stood second after Faba bean (CSA, 2015).

Common bean is the most common food legume in tropical Latin America and eastern and southern Africa and is cultivated as both bush and climbing growth habits (Beebe *etal*, 2011). In Ethiopia, dry beans are grown by small scale famers. They are major source of proteins in the lowlands where they are consumed as *Nifro*, *Wasa*, *Shirowat*, *soup* and *samosa* (Rubyogo *etal*, 2011). It is one of the fast expanding legume crops that provide an essential part of the daily diet and foreign earnings for most Ethiopians (Girma, 2009). The consumption of beans reduces of the risk of cancer, especially breast and colon cancer. This could be in part due to the significant amount of antioxidant activity found in the phenolic compounds in the seed coat of beans (Beninger and Hosfield, 2003). Beans are a rich source of folic acid which is especially important for women of child bearing age as low levels of folic acid during pregnancy can lead to neural tube defects in their infants (Gupta and Gupta, 2004).

Despite its importance, bean yields in developing countries are among the lowest in the world, with average of 0.5 tonnes ha⁻¹ (FAO, 2007) compared to 1–2 tonnes ha⁻¹ commonly reported in experimental fields. Across farming systems, biotic and abiotic stresses continue to present the major constraints for increased bean production and high yields with bean diseases representing the major constraints to production by reducing yields and seed quality. The progress in genetic and breeding improvement of bean, applying classical methods reached to his limits in many attitudes.

Due to a long process of breeding and selection, the bean genetic diversity has been very limited. Bean breeding programmes are well developed, but there are many limitations of the traditionally breeding methods coming from the low recombination potential due to the selfing process, low heritability of some important characteristics (total yields and yield components), and embryo abortion of some inter specific hybrids, etc. Then, alongside the conventional breeding techniques, a biotechnological tool such as tissues culture, *in vitro* mutagenesis, marker assisted breeding, and genetic transformation has been made to obtain improved common bean varieties.

TISSUE CULTURE IN COMMON BEAN

Plant tissue culture is the science of growing plant cells, tissues or organs isolated from the mother plant, on artificial media. It includes techniques and methods used to research into many botanical disciplines and has several practical objectives (George *etal.*, 2008). The potential of plant tissue culture includes: 1) Rapid multiplication of select genotypes, 2) Production of disease-free plants, 3) Germplasm preservation and 4) Genetic manipulation. In the last decade, much progress has been made in common bean tissue culture.

In Vitro Propagation of Common bean

Reliable and efficient *in vitro* culture systems that result in efficient differentiation shoot development and whole plant regeneration is an essential requirement for improvement of common bean through genetic transformation or mutagenesis (Svetleva et al. 2003). Direct or indirect Somatic embryogenesis and organogenesis realized Process of *in vitro* regeneration in common bean.

Different study has been conducted to establish the protocol for *in vitro* regeneration of common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.). Ahmed et al. 2002 reported *In vitro* plant regeneration of *Phaseolus* by organogenesis where as Schryer et al. 2005 also reported regeneration through somatic embryogenesis. Benjamín, et al, 2015 also achieve platelets of common bean by Direct Organogenesis.

Although several protocols have been described for bean regeneration, development of an optimal *in vitro* culture. Thảo *et al.*, 2013, developed A protocol for *in vitro* regeneration from cotyledonary nodes of 7 day-seedlings of common bean. Shoot induction medium was MSB5 + 11.1µM BAP + 0.5µM α-NAA, on which 86.7% of explants induced shoots with an average of 3.1 shoots/explant. 53.3% of shoots rooted with a mean of 1.7 roots/shoot on root induction medium MSB5 + 4.9µM IBA. 80% rooted plantlets survived during acclimatization in greenhouse. Chandra *et al.*, (2014). Studied the Effect of N6-benzylaminopurine and adenine sulphate in *In-vitro* plant regeneration of *Phaseolus vulgaris* L. The higher multiple shoot formation was obtained using Field bean > Garden bean > String bean > French bean > Flageolet bean. Moreover, the higher average of leaves was obtained using Field bean > Flageolet bean > French bean > String bean > Garden bean. He established an efficient and reproducible method for regeneration of the commercially important Indian common bean using BAP and AS. Arias, *et al* 2010 also developed *In vitro* plant regeneration system for common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) by effect of N6-benzylaminopurine and adenine sulphate.

Production of Disease-Free Plants

Meristem-tip culture is the excision of the organized apex of the shoot from a selected donor plant for subsequent *in vitro* culture. It could be used in mass propagation, elimination of viral pathogens (including seed borne viral infections in legumes) and germplasm preservation. The conditions of culture are regulated to allow only for organized outgrowth of the apex directly in to a shoot, without the intervention of any adventitious organs (1-3). Benediciö *et al.*, 1997 studied the growth and development of *Phaseolus vulgaris* L. cv. Zorin meristems *in vitro* and he reported opening results on meristem culture in *Phaseolus vulgaris*. He worked out a system for meristem regeneration, elongation, and rooting, and prepared the protocol for production of mature bean plants according to these results.

Genetic Transformation in Common bean

Gene transfer is a transfer of a gene from one DNA molecule to another DNA molecule. Genetic transformation is a powerful tool and an important technique for the study of plant functional genomics, i.e., gene discovery, new insights into gene function, and investigation of genetically controlled characteristics (Narusaka& Narusaka, 2004). It enables the introduction of foreign genes into crop plants, expeditiously creating new genetically modified organisms. Gene transfer

represents a relatively new possibility for the treatment of rare genetic disorders and common multi factorial diseases by changing the expression of a person's genes (Arat, 2001). Gene transformation and genetic engineering contribute to an overall increase in crop productivity. (Sinclair *et al.*, 2004). There are two most dominant technologies for transferring gene into plants: Agro bacterium-mediated transformation and biolistics. As plants have cell wall, the biolistics is very useful in the plant gene transfer (Rasco-Gaunt, 2001).

In common bean transformation; two methods are currently available, indirect gene transfer using a disarmed gram negative soil bacterium such as *Agrobacterium*, or direct gene transfer techniques mainly particle bombardment or electroporation (Kim and Minamikawa, 1997; Rech *et al.*, 2008).

The *Agrobacterium*-mediated transformation process includes the following steps: (1) Isolate genes of interest from the source organism. (2) Insert the transgene into the Tiplasmid. (3) Introduce the T-DNA containing-plasmid into *Agrobacterium*. (4) Attach the bacterium to the host cell. (5) Excise the T-strand from the T-DNA region. (6) Transfer and integrate T-DNA into the plant genome (Narusaka& Narusaka, 2004).

Fig.1. The Agrobacterium-mediated transformation process

Source, Narusaka& Narusaka (2004).

Plant transformation process using particle bombardment includes the following steps: (1) Isolate protoplasts from leaf tissues. (2) Inject DNA-coated particles into the protoplasts using particle gun. (3) Regenerate into whole plants. (4) Acclimate the transgenic plants in a greenhouse.

Fig. 2. Plant transformation process using particle bombardment

Source, (Narusaka& Narusaka, 2004).

Amugune *et al.*, (2011). Evaluated the potential of two common bean varieties Mwitemanía and Rose coco to in vitro *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*- mediated transformation. Transformed shoots and roots confirmed by histochemical staining for GUS activity was obtained in 40 weeks old Mwitemanía plantlets from explants infected with *A. tumefaciens* LBA 4404 (pBI 121) and No GUS expression was observed in all Rose coco and Mwitemanía shoots from explants infected with EHA 105 (pCAMBIA 1201) or EHA 105 (pCAMBIA 1301). Mc Clean *et al.* (1991) obtained transformed callus and roots from cotyledonary nodes and hypocotyls of dry bean infected with *A. tumefaciens* strain C58Z707 and avirulent *A. rhizogenes* strain A4RS (pRiB278b), respectively. The transformed callus and roots, though capable of growing on MS medium with 5 μM BAP and 50 mg L-1 kanamycin could not regenerate plants. A kanamycin resistant callus obtained from leaf disc or hypocotyl explants of green bean infected with *A. tumefaciens* EHA 101 (pKYLX71GUS) using SH (Franklin *et al.* 1993) Aragao *et al.*, (1998) reported a transgenic bean plants expressing resistance to bean golden mosaic geminivirus through particle bombardment. Rech *et al.*, (2008) also developed Transgenic bean plants tolerance to the herbicides glufosinate ammonium and imazapyr through particle bombardment. Kwapata *et al.* (2012). Conducted Genetic Transformation on Five common bean varieties, including “Condor,” “Matterhorn,” “Sedona,” “Olathe,” and “Montcalm” were genetically transformed via the Biolistic bombardment of the apical shoot meristem primordium. Transgenes included *gus* color marker which visually confirmed

transgenic events, the *bar* herbicide resistance selectable marker used for *in vitro* selection of transgenic cultures and which confirmed Liberty herbicide resistant plants, and the barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) late embryogenesis abundant protein (*HVA1*) which conferred drought tolerance with a corresponding increase in root length of transgenic plants.

MARKER ASSISTED SELECTION IN COMMON BEAN

According to (Ribaut, J. M and Hoisington, 1998; Kasha,1999; Xu et al., 2005) Justifications for the application of MAS in plant breeding fall into four broad areas that are relevant to almost all target crops

- ✓ Traits that are difficult to manage through conventional phenotypic selection because they are expensive or time-consuming to measure, or have low penetrance or complex inheritance
- ✓ Traits whose selection depends on specific environments or developmental stages that influence the expression of the target phenotypes
- ✓ Maintenance of recessive alleles during backcrossing or for speeding up backcross breeding in general
- ✓ Pyramiding multiple monogenic traits (such as pest and disease resistances or qualitative traits) or several QTL for a single target trait with complex inheritance (such as drought tolerance or other adaptive traits). Introgression and pyramiding of multiple genes affecting the same trait is a great challenge to breeding programs.

Several hindrances to the adoption of MAS as a general breeding strategy for polygenic traits, including

- ✓ Problems in accurately localizing and estimating the effects of the QTL
- ✓ The difficulty of improving the already substantial gains from selection when heritability is high
- ✓ Inability to infer QTL effects from one breeding cross to another
- ✓ Difficulty in integrating QTL mapping procedures into efficient breeding methods

Molecular Markers

Molecular markers are based on naturally occurring polymorphisms in DNA sequences (i.e. base pair deletion, substitutions, additions or patterns) (Gupta *et al.*, 1999). They are superior to both morphological and biochemical markers because they are relatively, abundant through the genome even in a highly inbred cultivars, completely independent of environmental conditions and can be detected at virtually any stage of plant development (O' Neill *et al.*, 2003).

DNA based markers provide very effective and reliable tool for measuring genetic diversity in crop germplasm and studying evolutionary relationships than other available techniques for assessing the genetic variability and relatedness among crop germplasm (Malik *et al.*, 2008). They can be applied in the identification of cultivars and clones, genetic mapping, marker assisted selection (MAS), population genetics, molecular systematics and etc (Weising *et al.*, 2005). According to Vithanage *et al* (1995) molecular markers are 'land marks' which can be

identified on the genome and, therefore, offer the best possible means of identifying individuals from biological samples. In recent years, different marker systems such as RFLP, RAPD, ISSR, STS, AFLP, SSR, SNPs, and others have been developed and applied to a range of crops (FAO, 2003).

Molecular markers can be classified in to two major groups: those based on DNA-DNA hybridization between a DNA or RNA ‘probe’ and total genomic DNA (eg. RFLP and dot-blot assay) non- PCR based; and, those based on the PCR amplification of genomic DNA fragments (eg. RAPD, ISSR, SCAR, SSR, AFLP, SNP, etc). DNA markers are used for germplasm evaluation, genetic diagnostics, phylogenetic analysis, study of genome organization and screening of transformants (Gupta et al. 1999). Molecular marker maps have been constructed for a wide range of crops

Identification of QTL

A QTL (Quantitative Trait Locus) is a chromosomal region supposed to contain a gene or genes that contribute to a quantitative trait. In QTL mapping experiments the genetic basis of quantitative traits is dissected into their single components. Many traits of agricultural importance are quantitative, i.e. based on polygenes. As environmental influences can have a considerable effect on the expression of these traits, DNA markers can have a great impact in breeding for such traits, because selection for quantitative traits normally requires large scale testing in various environments Brumlop and Finckh (2010).

In order to map QTLs, two homozygous inbred lines, differing in many phenotypic characteristics, are crossed to produce an F1 progeny. The uniformly heterozygous F1 is backcrossed to one or the other parental line resulting in a segregating mapping population, in which it can be monitored whether certain markers tend to co-segregate with specific phenotypes of interest that distinguish the parental lines. If co-segregation between a marker of known chromosomal location and a phenotype is observed, it is assumed that the genes contributing to the phenotype and the marker must be closely linked (Avisé, 2004). In this way it is possible to construct a genetic map, showing the position of QTLs for a certain trait on the different chromosomes. After this first step, QTL analysis can be applied to plant breeding and knowledge of QTL map locations is utilized for selection of improved varieties (Brumlop and Finckh 2010). Several researchers identified the QTL of different traits in common bean. Mukeshimana et al (2014) recorded a total of 14 QTL associated with yield and yield components (number of pods per plant, SW), pod harvest index, and phenology (number of days to flower and maturity) were consistently identified mainly on six chromosomes (Pv01, Pv03, Pv04, Pv07, Pv08, and Pv09) of the eleven common bean chromosomes. Beattie et al. (2003) mapped QTL for number of pods per plant on Pv03. Ambachew et al., (2006) identified a total of 11 Quantitative trait loci for pod harvest index, root pulling resistance, grain yield and bean stem maggot damage scores in recombinant inbred lines from a cross of BAT881 and G21212 using SSR and SNP markers. Augusta et al. (2012) worked out QTL mapping for the cooking time of common beans. Six significant QTLs with an LOD C 3.0 was found for the cooking time of the F2:4 and F2:5 generations. Blair et al., (2006) reported the identification of QTL in an advanced backcross population from a cross of an Andean bean ICA Cerinza with a wild bean accession G24404, Quantitative trait loci for pods per plant was mapped on Pv07, Pv09, and Pv11. Asrat and

Matthew (2012) identified A total of 15 putative QTL for seven rooting pattern traits and four shoot traits from A recombinant inbred line population of DOR364 and BAT477. Kamfwa et al (2013) conducted the Identification of QTL for Fusarium Root Rot Resistance in a resistant line MLB-49-89A of common bean. The major QTL appears to map close to the same region of Pv03. A major QTL with a logarithm of odds (LOD) score of 6.1 and R^2 of 34% was detected between PVBR87 and PVBR109 markers in the K132 population. The same markers were significantly associated with resistance in the K20 population ($R^2 = 14\%$, $P < 0.001$).

Kelly et al., 2003. evaluated SCAR markers BC420, SU91, and SAP6 linked with three major QTL on B6, B8, and B10 respectively (Fig 3). Mukeshimana, (2013) mapped QTL for number of pods per plant on Pv03 and Pv08 whereas Checa and Blair (2012) mapped QTL for number of pods per plant on Pv04 and Pv10

Figure 3. Agarose gel photograph depicting SCAR markers linked with QTL on putative linkage groups B10 (SAP6, lane 2), B8 (SU91, lane3), B6 (BC420, lane 4), and multiplexed in single PCR reactions for DNA from F₂ plants segregating for all three SCAR markers (lanes 6–12). Lanes 1 and 5 represent 100 bp ladder starting at 500 bp.

The QTL could facilitate marker-assisted selection to introgress resistance for different disease into the highly susceptible common bean genotypes.

Association mapping

The classical method of QTL identification is conducted by a bi-parental QTL mapping approach. Association analysis which does not require development of a bi-parental mapping population is becoming a common method of QTL mapping mainly due to its high resolution, broader allele coverage and cost effectiveness. In this method, diverse lines or cultivars can be used for obtaining information on marker-trait associations. It has the potential to identify QTL associated with a desired trait and even to detect the causal polymorphisms within a gene that are responsible for the difference in two alternative phenotypes (Gupta *et al.*, 2005). The resolution of QTL is high as only closely linked alleles are in LD due to a long history of recombination (Ingvarsson and Street, 2011). Association mapping is also useful for establishing associations between haplotype blocks and traits of interest. However, genomic locations of QTL detected by the association mapping approach need to be inferred from a consensus genetic map and/or physical map for the crop under study. Special mapping

populations known as Nested Association Mapping (NAM) populations allow simultaneous QTL detection and chromosomal position determination (Ersoz and Buckler, 2009).

The steps of association mapping analysis are: (1) selection of a group of individual lines or cultivars with wide genetic diversity to form the mapping population or panel; (2) recording the phenotypic characteristics; (3) genotyping the mapping population with available molecular markers; (4) quantification of the extent of LD for a chromosome and/or a genome using molecular marker data of the mapping panel; (5) assessment of the population structure and kinship (coefficient of relatedness between each pair of individuals); (6) determination of association of phenotypic and genotypic data based on the information gained from LD and Population structure using appropriate statistical methods (Abdurakhmonov and Abdugarimov, 2008).

Association mapping broadly falls into two major classes: (1) genome-wide association mapping, which surveys genetic variation in the whole genome using a large number of markers to detect regions associated with the phenotype (Zhu et al., 2008); and (2) candidate-gene association mapping, which relates within candidate gene polymorphisms with phenotypic variations of the traits. The choice between whole genome scanning and candidate gene approaches depends on the extent of LD in the population and the availability of markers. Although genome-wide association is a promising approach for scanning the entire genome for detecting marker-trait associations with a large number of markers, the candidate gene approach is also important to map targeted genes with known function (Tabor et al., 2002). The association mapping approach has been used for several crops to identify QTL and also to characterize candidate genes (Erena, 2013).

Shi et al. (2011) carried out Association mapping of common bacterial blight resistance QTL in Ontario bean breeding populations. Mixed Linear Mode analysis, including population structure and kinship, was used to discover marker-trait associations. Eighteen and 22 markers were significantly associated with CBB rating at 14 and 21 Days After Inoculation, respectively. Fourteen markers were significant for both dates and the markers UBC420, SU91, g321, g471, and g796 were highly significant. Nemli *et al.*, (2014) conducted Association mapping for five agronomic traits in the common bean. Sixty-two marker-trait associations was identified for the five traits. Five markers (SNP1, M-CAA/E-AAC, M-CAA/E-AAG, M-GAT/E-ACT and M-GAT/E-AGT) had common associations for four traits, including PF, PT, GH and DF. also, certain markers like SSR-Bmd1 with PF, SSR- Bmd45 with SSP, and SNP6 and SNP50 only associated with GH trait.

Genome Wide Association Mapping

Genome-wide association mapping is becoming a widespread method to identify quantitative trait loci (QTL). Its benefit over traditional bi-parental mapping approaches depends on the extent of linkage disequilibrium (LD) in the mapping population and dense marker coverage across the genome (Zhu *et al.*, 2008);.

Source, Zhu *et al* (2008)

Fig.4. Schematic diagram and contrast of genome-wide association mapping and candidate-gene association mapping. The inclusion of population structure (Q), relative kinship (K), or both in final association analysis depends on the genetic relationship of the association mapping panel and the diversity of the trait examined. For GWAS, a large number of markers are tested for association with the trait of interest, and prior knowledge regarding candidate genes is not required. It works best for a research consortium with complementary expertise and adequate funding. For CGAS, candidate genes are selected based on prior knowledge of the trait of interest, and a hypothesis-driven, and trait-specific approach is used. It is a low-cost approach but will miss other unknown loci.

Very few studies have been conducted in genome-wide study in common bean. Cichy *et al* (2015), conducted genome-wide association analysis (GWAS) to identify genomic regions influencing cooking time trait, and to test the ability to predict cooking time by raw seed characteristics on a panel of 206 *P. vulgaris* accessions. Based on the result, GWAS revealed regions on chromosomes Pv02, Pv03, and Pv06 associated with cooking time. Significant SNPs associated with cooking time were found on chromosomes Pv02, Pv03, and Pv06 (Fig.5). Kamfwa *et al.* (2015) conducted a genome-wide association study (GWAS) to explore the genetic basis of variation for symbiotic nitrogen fixation (SNF) and related traits in the Andean Diversity Panel (ADP). Reported a Significant SNPs and candidate genes for symbiotic nitrogen fixation (SNF) and related traits were identified on Pv03, Pv07 and Pv09 chromosomes of common bean.

Fig. 5 a Manhattan plot of cooking time averaged across 2012 and 2013 of 206 Andean Diversity Panel accessions with 3741 SNP (>0.02 minor allele frequency) and mapping conducted with Multiple Linear Model using a kinship matrix and 2 principal components to account for population structure. The *blue line* is the False Discovery Rate (3.99×10^{-5}) threshold for significance and the red line is $p = 0.005$ threshold for significance.

Perseguini *et al* (2016), conducted Genome-Wide Association Studies of Anthracnose and Angular Leaf Spot Resistance in Common Bean and reported Using SNPs, 21 and 17 significant statistically associations were obtained for ANT and angular ALS, respectively, providing more associations with this marker. The SSR-IAC167 and PvM95 markers, both located on chromosome Pv03, and the SNP scaffold00021_89379, were associated with both diseases. The other markers were distributed across the entire common bean genome, with chromosomes Pv03 and Pv08 showing the greatest number of loci associated with ANT resistance. The chromosome Pv04 was the most saturated one, with six markers associated with ALS resistance. The telomeric region of this chromosome showed four markers located between approximately 2.5 Mb and 4.4 Mb. The results demonstrate the great potential of genome-wide association studies to identify QRLs related to ANT and ALS in common bean. The results indicate a quantitative and complex inheritance pattern for both diseases in common bean.

Fig.6. Representative map of the genome positions of markers associated with ANT and ALS resistance. SSR and SNP markers were located on the reference genome (Schmutz et al., 2014) using the Phytozome v1.0 BLAST tool (<http://www.phytozome.net/>). Markers in blue are associated with ANT resistance and those in red are associated with ALS resistance. The SSR-IAC167, PVM95, and scafold00021_89379 markers (green) were associated with resistance to both diseases. The map was drawn with MapChart (Voorrips 2002), and marker positions are represented in Mb.

Shi *et al.* (2011) reported Fourteen markers were significant for both days after inoculation (DAI) and five markers were highly significant (P B 0.001), including BC420 and SU91a after conducting genome-wide association mapping in a bean breeding population to detect the markers associated to CBB resistance Kamfwa *et al.* (2015), after conducting Genome-Wide Association Study of Agronomic Traits in Common Bean, significant SNP markers associated with several agronomic traits were identified. Significant SNPs for seed yield were identified on Pv03 and Pv09.

Figure.7. Manhattan plots showing candidate single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) and their P-values from genome-wide Association study using mixed linear model for seed yield (kg ha⁻¹) on Pv03 and Pv09. Red line is the significance threshold of $P = 1.03 \times 10^{-5}$ after Bonferonni correction of $\alpha = 0.05$

Candidate Genes association mapping

Candidate-gene association mapping is a hypothesis driven approach to complex trait dissection, with biologically relevant candidates selected and ranked based on the evaluation of available results from genetic, biochemical, or physiology studies in model and non-model plant species (Mackay, 2001; Risch and Merikangas, 1996). Because SNPs offer the highest resolution for mapping QTL and are potentially in LD with the causative polymorphism they are the preferential candidate-gene variant to genotype in association studies (Rafalski, 2002).

Candidate-gene association mapping requires the identification of SNPs between lines and within specific genes. Therefore, the most straightforward method of identifying candidate gene SNPs relies on the resequencing of amplicons from several genetically distinct individuals of a larger association population.

Fewer diverse individuals in the SNP discovery panel are needed to identify common SNPs, whereas many more are needed to identify rarer SNPs. Promoter, intron, exon, and 5'/3'-untranslated regions are all reasonable targets for identifying candidate gene SNPs, with non-coding regions expected to have higher levels of nucleotide diversity than coding regions. The rate of LD decay for a specific candidate gene locus dictates the number of SNPs per unit length

(e.g., kb) needed to identify significant associations (Whitt and Buckler, 2003). Therefore, the number and base-pair length of amplicons required to sufficiently sample a candidate gene locus is almost entirely dependent on LD and SNP distribution, with a higher density of SNP markers needed in regions of relatively low LD and high nucleotide diversity (Zhu et al., 2008);

Burt *et al.* (2015) studied the Identification of Candidate Gene with SNP Marker-Based Fine Mapping of Anthracnose Resistance Gene *Co-4*. *Co-42* is the most effective anthracnose resistance gene characterized to date (Balardin and Kelly, 1998). Alleles at the *Co-4* locus confer resistance to a number of races of *C. lindemuthianum*. A population of 94 F4:5 recombinant inbred lines of a cross between resistant black bean genotype B09197 and susceptible navy bean cultivar Nautica was used to identify markers associated with resistance in bean chromosome 8 (Pv08) where *Co-4* is localized. Thirty two unique annotated candidate genes was identified that spanned a physical region of 936.46 kb.

Marker-assisted backcrossing (MABC)

Backcrossing is used in plant breeding to transfer (introgress) favorable traits from a donor plant into an elite genotype (recurrent parent). In repeated crossings the original cross is backcrossed with the recurrent parent until most of the genes stemming from the donor are eliminated (Becker 1993). However, the donor segments attached to the target allele can remain relatively large, even after many backcrossing generations. In order to minimize this linkage drag, marker assays can be of advantage (Frisch et al. 1999). Markers can be used in the context of MABC to either control the target gene (foreground selection) or to accelerate the reconstruction of the recurrent parent genotype (background selection). According to Tanksley et al. (1989), in traditional backcross breeding the reconstruction of the recurrent parent genotype requires more than six generations, while this may be reduced to only three generations in MABC. At the moment MABC also is and will probably remain the preferred means of backcrossing transgenes into elite inbred lines, which is also considerably contributing to its popularity (Ragot & Lee 2007). MABC is especially efficient if a single allele is to be transferred into a different genetic background.

The SCAR marker (*Phs*) linked with white mold resistance, detects a major-effect QTL that is expressed in both greenhouse (38%) and field (26%) environments, but successful MAS for the QTL has not yet been reported (Miklas et al., 2001). Miklas (2007) conducted Marker-Assisted Backcrossing QTL for Partial Resistance to Sclerotinia White Mold in Dry Bean. He was successful in backcrossing resistance from G122 into susceptible Pinto bean using *Phs* SCAR for temperate conditions, whereas Carneiro et al., (2010) results the SCAR *Phs* is not efficient in marker-assisted selection in common beans for white mold physiological resistance adapted in the tropical, because there the QTL from G122 did not express in the present conditions due to its interaction by environments, although it expressed large effect in temperate conditions. He was achieved the SSR markers are efficient in identifying individuals with a greater proportion of the recurrent genome. Similarly (Miklas and Kelly, 2002) by using MAS-backcrossing rapidly introgress the *Co-42* resistance gene into pinto bean to combat the emerging anthracnose disease problem in North Dakota.

Marker-assisted recurrent selection (MARS)

The improvement of complex traits via phenotypic recurrent selection is generally possible, but the long selection cycles impose restrictions on the practicability of this breeding method. With the use of markers, recurrent selection can be accelerated considerably. In continuous nursery programs pre flowering genotypic information is used for marker assisted selection and controlled pollination. Thus, several selection-cycles are possible within one year, accumulating favorable QTL alleles in the breeding population (Eathington *et al.* 2007).

Additionally, it is possible today to define an ideal genotype as a pattern of QTLs, all QTLs carrying favorable alleles from various parents. If individuals are crossed based on their molecular marker genotypes, it might be possible to get close to the ideal genotype after several successive generations of crossings. It is likely that through such a MARS breeding scheme higher genetic gain will be achieved than through MABC (Ribaut & Ragot 2006). Concepts how to achieve the ideal genotype using multi trait selection indices have been developed (Peleman & Van der Voort 2003).

Pyramiding

Using MAS, several genes can be combined into a single genotype. Pyramiding is also possible through conventional breeding but phenotypically testing individual plants for 11 traits can be time-consuming and sometimes very difficult. The most frequent strategy of pyramiding is combining multiple resistance genes. Different resistance genes can be combined in order to develop broad-spectrum resistance to, e.g., diseases and insects. Either qualitative resistance genes can be combined or quantitative resistances controlled by QTLs (Brumlop & Finckh, 2011).

As a result of Ana *et al.*,(2012) study, genetic resistance to three anthracnose races controlled by genes included in clusters Co-2 and Co-3/9, and genetic resistance to BCM controlled by genotype I + bc-3 was combined in the fabada line A3308. Kiryowa *et al.* (2015) was made three-way crosses to pyramid three anthracnose and one *pythium* root rot resistance genes in four susceptible market class varieties . Sequence characterized amplified regions (SCAR) markers were used to facilitate the pyramiding scheme. Finally pyramiding higher numbers of resistance genes may cause a grain yield reduction via number of seeds per plant. Because Number of pyramided genes had significant negative indirect effect on seed weight per plant only through number of seeds per plant. It is important for breeders to simultaneously select for number of pyramided genes with number of seeds per plant and other highly associated traits. Negative correlations between the number of pyramided genes and several agronomic traits was observed. Mukankusi *et al.*,(2016), after conducting the Gene pyramiding resistance to major diseases of common bean . SCAR, CAPS and SSR, were utilized in the gene pyramiding schemes. Gene transfer success and agronomic performance of developed lines was evaluated. Three resistance genes to anthracnose, and one resistance gene to *pythium* root rot , Five resistance genes to ALS , Six resistance genes to ALS, BCMNV, anthracnose and *pythium* root rot and Quantitative resistance to *Fusarium* root rot from four parents. Obala *et al.*, (2010) determined the effectiveness

of pyramided *Fusarium* root rot (FRR) resistance genes and validated association of SSR PVBR87 marker with FRR resistance in common bean. A double cross (DC) involving four resistance sources was used to accumulate FRR resistance genes into one background. The DC F1 and each resistant line were crossed to two susceptible cultivars. Parents, F1 and F2 populations were subjected to FSP-3 in a screen house. Two single cross (SC) F2 populations were screened with SSR PVBR87 marker. Five parent crosses performed better than single crosses. SSR PVBR87 marker showed association with FRR resistance in the two SC F2 populations. Bueno *et al.* (1999). Incorporated multiple resistances to Empoasca, Apion and Zabrotes through single seed descent and evaluation of a large population of segregant. Mutlu *et al.* (2005) examined the pyramiding of multiple QTL for CBB resistance into a single pinto bean (*P. vulgaris*) genotype. The results from that study differed from those observed in this study in that the combination of multiple QTL for CBB resistance provided a higher level of resistance than that conferred by either QTL alone.

Pyramiding resistance genes seems an intelligent strategy. However, phenotypic selection cannot be carried out due to the lack of differentiating virus strains. Thus, MAS offers promising opportunities. Suitable strategies have been developed for pyramiding genes against the BaYMV complex. What has to be taken into account when applying such strategies in practical breeding is the fact that the pyramiding has to be repeated after each crossing, because the pyramided resistance genes are segregating in the progeny (Werner *et al.* 2005).

Omics Technologies

The new "global" methods of measuring families of cellular molecules, such as RNA, proteins, and intermediary metabolites have been termed "-omic" technologies, based on their ability to characterize all, or most, members of a family of molecules in a single analysis. With these new tools, we can now obtain complete assessments of the functional activity of biochemical pathways, and of the structural genetic (sequence) differences among individuals and species, that were previously unattainable. The terms 'Ome' and 'Omics' are derivations of the suffix *-ome*, which has been appended to a variety of previously existing biological terms to create names for fields of endeavor like genome, proteome, transcriptome and metabolome that are either speculative or have some tangible meaning in particular contexts (Debnath *etal.*, 2010). Omics technologies provide the tools needed to look at the differences in DNA, RNA, proteins, and other cellular molecules between species and among individuals of a species. (Aardema&MacGregor, 2002). Omics has become the new mantra of molecular biology. 'Omic' technologies include genomics, transcriptomics (gene expression profiling), proteomics and metabolomics. The technology platform of genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics and metabolomics are high-throughput technologies. They increase substantially the number of proteins/genes that can be detected simultaneously and have the potential to relate complex mixtures to complex effects in the form of gene/protein expression profiles. (Debnath *etal.*, 2010).

Fig.8. The Central Dogma and the interacting “ome” includes the study of genome, proteome, transcriptome and metabolome

Source, Debnath *et al.*, (2010)

Mensack *et al.* (2010) Evaluated the diversity among common beans from two centers of domestication using “Omics ” technologies. On proteomics study, A 2-DGE analysis revealed differences among cultivated and wild-type common bean cultivars as evidenced from differences in number as well as abundance of protein spots on gels, and used these factors to classify these cultivars based on their Centre of Domestications. Torres *et al.* (2007) Studied Gel-based proteomics reveals potential novel protein markers of ozone stress in leaves of cultivated bean and maize species. His result tells, abiotic stresses have examined the effect of the gaseous pollutant ozone, revealing distinct protein changes in affected leaves by two-dimensional electrophoresis (2-DGE). Zadražnik *et al.*, (2013) studied Differential proteomic analysis of drought stress response in leaves of common bean. Based on 2D-DIGE analysis, showed the impact of drought stress on different biological pathways and molecular functions in leaves of drought tolerant and sensitive cultivars. Yang *et al.*, (2013). Conducted a research on Proteomic and phosphoproteomic analysis of polyethylene glycol-induced osmotic stress in root tips of common bean. The Phosphoproteomic analysis revealed that improved phosphorylation of dehydrin acting a major protective role in the reversibility of cell wall extensibility during recovery from osmotic stress induced physical breakdown of cell wall structures. Comparative Proteomic Analysis of Two Varieties of Genetically Modified (GM) Common Bean and Their Non-GM Counterparts, His Analyses detected 23 spots differentially accumulated between GM Perola and non-GM Perola and 21 spots between GM Pontal and non-GM Pontal, although they were not the same proteins in Perola and Pontal varieties, indicating that the variability observed may not be due to the genetic transformation. Among them, eight proteins were identified in Perola varieties, and four proteins were identified in Pontal (Balsamo *et al.*, 2015).

Summary and Recommendation

Common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris L.*) improvement objectives have been successful using conventional breeding methods to accomplish a wide breeding strategy. Success include the identification of stable genotype, the development of cultivars with resistance to biotic and abiotic stress. Bean breeding programmes are well developed, but there are many limitations of the traditionally breeding methods coming from the low recombination potential due to the selfing process, low heritability of some important characteristics (total yields and yield

components), and embryo abortion of some inter specific hybrids, etc. Then, alongside the conventional breeding techniques, a biotechnological tool such as tissues culture, in vitro mutagenesis, Identification of quantitative trait loci (QTLs) with marker assisted breeding and genetic transformation has been made to obtain improved common bean varieties. Many bean improvement programs use molecular markers to facilitate cultivar development. Several recent germplasm releases have used molecular markers to introgress and or pyramid major genes and QTL for disease resistance. Genetic mapping in common bean for different traits is facilitated by highly polymorphic and co-dominant microsatellite based markers and studied from different researchers. Marker assisted selection (MAS) also a good progress and identified a superior targeting of required genes especially for biotic and abiotic stress. Regardless of this, Therefore, future plan (work) will focus on the following.

- The Continuing of combined application of biotechnological and conventional approaches for the achieving of rapid genetic enhancement.
- Integrated approaches in Genomics, Metabolomics ,Bioinformatics and Proteomics will have to be used together for better analysis.
- Continuing searching of additional sources of gene and testing of genotypes for biotic and a biotic stress before the reaching of severity of the problem.
- There is a need to assess genetic variability for various nutritional and ant- nutritional traits in the germplasm of cultivated and wild species
- The environmental condition is sequentially chancing there must be focused on the developing of varieties for different agro-ecological condition to mitigating the problem through the integration of conventional to molecular tools.

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